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**Structuring the Individual Plan of Professional Development (IPPD)
For Teachers in the Advancement of Career Demand Growth**
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Abstract:

This research assessed the implementation of the Individual Plan of Professional Development (IPPD) towards career demand growth for secondary public-school teachers in South District 7 at Cebu City Division, Cebu City school year 2021-2022 as bases for a developmental action plan. Findings of this study reveal that the school heads and teacher-respondents belong to the age group of 31-40 years old, female, married, obtained units in their master’s degree, have been linked with the institution for more than 6 years, have a performance rating of very satisfactory, and attended national trainings, seminars, and workshops. Looking into the extent of implementation of the individual plan of professional development (IPPD) which is divided into five indicators – professional development in school; learning through professional development; participation experience in IPPD; impact on learners; and attitude and beliefs, accumulated an overall grand mean of 4.27, which means that the respondents strongly agree that the extent of implementation of the IPPD across all indicators increases their career demand growth. When testing the relationship between the profile of respondents and extent of implementation of individual plan for professional development, age, length of service, and highest educational attainment rejected the null hypothesis which means that these profiles of teachers are significantly related with their extent of implementation of individual plan for professional development. In the focus group discussion, the teachers reveal that the implementation of IPPD gives greater insights and improves performance; allows putting into practice the appropriate trainings, and seminars attended; and impacts students’ learning and behavior. Lastly, pertaining to the challenges and barriers in the implementation of the individual plan of professional development, most of the teacher-respondents believe that time constraint is their main challenge or barrier in terms of the implementation of the IPPD towards career demand growth for the public secondary school teachers.

Keywords: Cebu City Division, Descriptive Method, Development Education, Developmental Action Plan, Individual Plan of Professional Development, Philippines

Introduction:

Education is a never-ending process. It does not end with obtaining a degree and beginning a profession. Career-focused individuals may continually enhance their knowledge, skills, and attitude and become more effective at their employment by engaging in continuing education. It is vital for school administrators in the field of K-12 education administration to encourage teachers to pursue professional development, not only to ensure the best learning outcomes for their students, but also to be more effective and satisfied in various aspects of their work.

Educational technology, school district guidelines and curriculum standards are constantly changing, making it challenging for teachers to keep up with new trends and best practices in the field. Professional development transforms teachers into better and more apt educators by enabling them to create relevant and tailored course instructions for today’s students. In fact, the Department of Education began to take a closer look at professional development of teachers or the post training of teachers because student achievement was becoming a serious source of concern nationwide.

Relatively, four decades ago, a strong push towards improving professional development evolved. Dillon (1976) points that the additional work teachers were required to undertake was unfortunately not always directed specifically at making professional teachers more competent or better qualified to educate children. Over thirty years later, however, with multifarious changes to societal and global needs, and with a very different student dynamic than existed a long time ago, professional development is more vital than ever before and needs to be revamped to meet the needs of changing worlds. Teachers must learn new strategies for coping with the diverse demands of students.

Today, the Department of Education is actively implementing fundamentals reforms that includes efforts for human resource development at all levels to sustain quality performance of school and learners. The Department’s package of policy reforms known as the Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda (BESRA) seeks “to systematically improve critical, regulatory, institutional, structural, financial, cultural, physical and informational conditions affecting basic education provision, access and delivery on the ground. These policy reforms are expected to create

critical change necessary to further accelerate, broaden, deepen and sustain the improved education effort already being started" (BESRA PIP. 2016).

Professional development is the only strategy school systems have to strengthen educators' performance levels. The professional development gives educator a better performance and raise student achievements. At present, there is a growing need to upgrade teaching profession. At the school level teacher can be developed. Many schemes and means can be initiated by the school heads which will help the teacher in their professional development which includes seminars and trainings.

In this study, the researcher wants to find out the extent of structuring the individual plan of professional development for teachers in the advancement of career demand growth. Being a school leader in this area, he considers this research to have a great importance for the teachers, learners, and the overall success of the school. This analysis is also carried out to develop action plan for public secondary school teachers.

Literature Review:

On a daily basis, teachers confront complex decisions that rely on many different kinds of knowledge and judgment and that can involve high-stakes outcomes for students' futures. To make good decisions, teachers must be aware of the many ways in which student learning can unfold in the context of development, learning differences, language and cultural influences, and individual temperaments, interests, and approaches to learning. In addition to foundational knowledge about these areas of learning and performance, teachers need to know how to take the steps necessary to gather additional information that will allow them to make more grounded judgments about what is going on and what strategies may be helpful. Above all, teachers need to keep what is best for the child at the center of their decision-making (Bransford, DarlingHammond, & LePage, 2017).

Educational reform developments are setting bold goals for student learning. Recent research literature suggests that while many factors contribute to achieving these goals, what teachers know and are able to do is one of the most important factors influencing student learning (Fullan, Hill & Crevola, 2016; Wilson, Floden & Ferrini-Mundy, 2021). The teachers' self-efficacy as a result of their continuous professional growth will certainly help to develop students' engagement with context and learning in general, creating an exciting learning environment (Kilag, 2022).

Current literature also stresses that the act of teaching is becoming increasingly complex and that highly competent teachers continue to learn, are adaptive, build up a sophisticated pedagogical repertoire, and are able to apply a range of practices for varying purposes that incorporate and integrate different kinds of knowledge, used in various combinations flexibly and fluently (Bransford, DarlingHammond & LePage, et. al, 2017).

Not surprisingly, there has been increasing attention to, and debate about, the essential role of deliberate, ongoing, high quality professional learning and development in supporting teachers to be responsive to changing, complex and challenging demands (Berliner, et.al, 2021). Fullan, Hill & Crevola, (2017) claim, for example, that professional learning that focuses on contextually-based, personalized, data-driven instruction is one of the three central components of Breakthrough thinking that will be critical to successful educational reform and that will noticeably improve and sustain learning for students and teachers alike. In their view, teachers must be learning in their classrooms every day.

Recent literature reveals a growing interest in professional development initiatives designed to address the professional development needs of mid-career teachers. A variety of studies have been undertaken that explore the complexities of effective professional development for midcareer teachers. These studies illuminate a range of factors that need to be carefully considered when determining appropriate delivery modes, standards and/or approaches for assessing professional learning (Berliner, et.al, 2017).

Study groups and writing groups, professionally oriented graduate programs, use of action research and lesson study methodologies at school sites, career ladder schemes, differentiated certification and incentives are only some of the approaches to professional development that have been undertaken. While many of these methods appear to have some efficacy in professional learning, there is no consensus in the literature regarding outcomes and clearly no panacea. Context, the unique professional knowledge of the teacher-learner, school and system supports and initiatives and a myriad of other factors must be considered in designing and determining high quality professional development.

The impact of infrequent, poorly designed and/or inadequately delivered approaches to teachers' professional development is evident in the literature. Not only costly, some approaches to professional development, as Warren-Little reminds us, continue to be dominated by a "one size fits all", transmission orientation to learning and in many ways are unproductive. "Nothing has promised so much and been so frustratingly wasteful as the

thousands of workshops and conferences that led to no significant change in practice when teachers returned to their classrooms". These strategies for professional learning, it is now understood, are no longer sufficient.

Professional Development for Experienced Teachers. Professional development is understood and described in different ways. Joyce et al. for example, defined professional development as "formal and informal provisions for the improvement of educators as people, educated persons, and professionals, as well as in terms of the competence to carry out their assigned roles." Gall and Renchler described professional development more specifically as "efforts to improve teachers' capacity to function as effective professionals by having them learn new knowledge, attitudes and skills." Fullan defined professional development as "the sum total of formal and informal learning pursued and experienced by the teacher in a compelling learning environment under conditions of complexity and dynamic change." Indeed, Fullan, Hill and Crevola (2017) have begun to intentionally use "professional learning" to refer to the ongoing, focused "daily learning of teachers individually and collectively", finding professional development a "more narrow conceptual term." Day's definition perhaps best highlights teachers' continuous professional learning within the broader context of change and its interconnected elements.

Not surprisingly, professional development for teachers is often located in one or more paradigms. Generally, scholars criticize the "deficit" paradigm articulated by Gall and Renchler above that characterizes professional development as targeted to compensating for a lack in skills or knowledge and viewing teachers as empty vessels "to be filled" Garmston. Some locate it within a "professional growth" paradigm that characterizes development as more self-directed arising from the learner's interests and needs (Feiman-Nemser, 2021). Some locate it within an "educational change" paradigm which views development as focused upon bringing about change (Fullan, Hill & Crevola, 2016; Warren-Little, 2021). Still others position professional development within a "problem solving" paradigm which links development to making improvements to address identified issues like student achievement needs (Joyce & Showers, 2021; McLaughlin & Zarrow, 2021). Guskey emphasizes and connects the growth and problem-solving notions of professional development, suggesting it is "increasingly seen as a process, not an event, ...that the process is intentional...and is a systematic effort to bring about positive change or improvement." Many other researchers call for a similarly integrative view of professional development (Day et al., 2017).

Professional development for experienced teachers is most often discussed in the literature as a segment or phase within a career long or continuing professional development (CPD) process. Within the continuum of teacher development, professional development for experienced teachers includes different components and takes many forms. Fullan, Hill & Crevola, (2017) claim, for example, that professional learning that focuses on contextually-based, personalized, data-driven instruction is one of the three central components of Breakthrough thinking that will be critical to successful educational reform and that will noticeably improve and sustain learning for students and teachers alike. In their view, teachers must be learning in their classrooms every day. Coherence is a critical feature of successful professional development approaches. Goals and standards, processes and practices, and assessment approaches of professional development need to have transparent, meaningful, and manageable standards and demonstrable outcomes that align and are integrated with student learning, organizational and societal learning needs and purposes.

Underpinning and shaping any particular learning process is ongoing consideration of multiple and interconnected factors including: student and teacher learning and performance; the learning context; the realities of the day-to-day work of teachers; research and knowledge bases that inform the act of teaching; teacher's interests and level of development; independent and collaborative learning activities and processes that are responsive to teachers' different ways and levels of learning and knowing; accountability and ways of assessing professional growth; meaningful, and manageable standards for teachers; alignment among personal, school and system goals; and attention to broader change processes (e.g. a sustained timeframe, varied forms of pressure and support).

Methodology:

This part contains the research methodology which includes the method to be used, the flow of the study, research environment, research respondents, research instruments, data gathering procedures, statistical treatment of data, scoring procedures and definition of terms.

Design

The design of this research was descriptive-correlational engaging quantitative approach to determine the extent of professional accountability of secondary school teachers in Cebu City Division towards individual plan of professional development.

Flow of the Study

The input of the study included the relevant information of the teacher-respondents in terms of their age, gender, civil status, highest educational attainment, length of service, performance rating, and relevant trainings, seminars

and workshops attended. This also covered the extent of implementation of the individual plan of professional development, as perceived by the respondents. The testing of relationship between the profile of the respondents and the extent of professional accountability of secondary school towards individual plan of professional development was also taken into consideration. Lastly, this also dealt with the challenges and barriers in the implementation of the individual plan of professional development towards career demand growth.

The process of the study included the research procedure that was strictly followed guided by the research approach it employed which was the descriptive-correlational design of research. The output of the study was the action plan for public secondary school teachers.

The environment of this study was the different secondary schools of South District 7 of Cebu City Division.

Secondary Schools in South District 7 are Inayawan Night High School, Bulacao National High School, Sinsin National High School, Bitlang Integrated School and Sudlon National High School. Inayawan Night High School started way back S.Y. 1994-1995 with more than 26 years in the making. At the very start, Night High Schools were made as Annex Schools of bigger High Schools, since it's quite small and a starter school yet in its very essence.

Many administrators were assigned (one after the other) to the school to date with fifty-six (59) teachers now and population of more than 2000 students (latest enrollment data S.Y. 2021-2022). Bulacao Community High School was first established as a Night High School in 1996. Currently, S.Y. 2021-2022, Bulacao Community High School has Dr. Edwin Sagayno Cablao as its school principal. It has 62 strong teaching and non-teaching personnel, which includes (1) School Principal, (1) Assistant Principal, (3) Assisting Principals Designate, (3) Master Teachers, (1) Registrar, (1) ADAS II, (2) MOOE-paid Utility Workers, (2) School Guards, and (1) LSB-paid staff. Sinsin National High School is located on the farthest end portion. The school site is just a mere kilometer away from the border between Cebu City and Toledo City where the farthest edges of the Atlas Mining Territory can be easily seen from the school.

There are ten (12) committed personnel, nine (9) are teachers and one (3) non teaching personnel. Eight (8) teachers who are all under the regular permanent status for Junior High School and one (1) teacher for the Senior High School. Three (3) are Teacher I, four (4) teachers with Master's Degree units, and two (2) teachers are Master's Degree holder. Out of nine (9) teachers, three (3) teachers are permanent resident of Sinsin and the rest are renting a house near the school. Bitlang Integrated School is at the heart of the mountain. It was established in early 1970's at sitio Bitlang. It only offered Grade One, Two and Three in a two-classroom building with only one teacher. The school was rebuilt in sitio Tabla because it was destroyed by a typhoon. However, its name was not changed and stood bear the name Bitlang Elementary School. The entire school site area is 10,000 square meters. It was donated by the late Juan S. Abella. It is approximately 23 km. away from the national highway.

The name of the school became Bitlang Integrated School when the high school department was established in 2007. Sudlon National High School was established in June 1977 wherein according to the folks in Sudlon II, in the earlier days, the Moncadistas, a religious organization founded by Dr. Hilario Camino Moncado and headed by Federico Jayme, initiated the request of having a school in the place. It was in 1987 that the school was turned over together with all its school buildings, books, properties and even the teachers. From Sudlon Barangay High School, it was renamed to Sudlon National High School, Sudlon Integrated School and currently Sudlon National High School.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were the 100 public secondary school teachers and 5 school heads of South District 7 at Cebu City Division. The respondents were chosen using purposive random sampling. The inclusion criteria were as follows: a] that they are teachers and school heads of Cebu City, Cebu; b] that they have been in the profession for more than a year; and c] that they are willing to participate and cooperate in the said undertaking. Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents.

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Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents.

Table 1

Distribution of Respondents

Cebu City Division	Respondents			
	School Heads	Teachers	Total	Percentage
Inayawan Night High School	1	21	22	21
Bulacao National High School	1	40	41	39
Sinsin National High School	1	9	10	9.52
Bitlang Integrated School	1	10	11	10.4
Sudlon National High School	1	20	21	20
Total	5	100	105	100

Instrument

The main questionnaire of this study was a modified standardized questionnaire taken from the study of Landar (2014) on "Implementation of Individual Plan of Professional Development (IPPD) of Public Elementary School Teachers in the First District of IloIlo". The tool was divided into three (3) parts.

The first part solicited information about the profile of the teacher-respondents as to their age, gender, highest educational attainment, length of service, performance rating, and relevant training, seminars, and workshops attended.

The second part of the questionnaire dealt with the extent of implementation of the individual plan of professional development in terms of Professional development in school; Learning through professional development; Participation experience in IPPD; Impact on learners; and Attitude and beliefs in teaching and learning. This was composed of 30 items and was measured using a 5-point Likert scale: 5 for STRONGLY AGREE, 4 for AGREE, 3 for UNDECIDED, 2 for DISAGREE, and 1 for STRONGLY DISAGREE.

Meanwhile, the third and last part identified the challenges and barriers in the implementation of the individual plan of professional development for public secondary school teachers.

Data Gathering Procedure

This research followed a step-by-step process in the conduct of this research endeavor.

First, a letter was made address to the Schools Superintendent of the Division of Cebu City for approval of the conduct of the study.

After the letter was approved, the questionnaires were personally distributed to the respondents. The respondents were given ample time of preferably 20-30 minutes to answer the questionnaire.

Data was then collected and submitted to the statistician for statistical treatment. It was subjected to further presentation, analysis, and interpretation with the guidance of the research adviser. The final draft was submitted for finalization and corrections.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following were the statistical procedures that were used by the researcher in the presentation and interpretation of the data.

Simple Percentage. This determined the profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of their age, gender, civil status, highest educational attainment, length of service, performance rating, and relevant trainings, seminars and workshops attended.

Mean. Computation of the mean was employed to determine the extent of implementation of the individual plan of professional development in terms of Professional development in the school district; Learning through professional development; Participation experience in IPPD; Impact on learners; and Attitude and beliefs through IPPD.

Chi-square. This determined the relationship between the profile of the respondents and the extent of implementation of the individual plan of professional development.

Scoring Procedures. The following were the scoring procedures:

Weight	Range	Response Category	Verbal Description
5	4.21 - 5.00	Strongly Agree	this means that one strongly favors the statement without a little disagreement
4	3.41 - 4.20	Agree	this means that one favors the statement with a little disagreement
3	2.61 - 3.40	Undecided	this means that one is yet to decide whether he/she agrees or not
2	1.81 - 2.60	Disagree	this means that one is not in favor with the statement but with a little agreement
1	1.00 -1.80	Strongly Disagree	this means that one strongly is not in favor with the statement without a little agreement

RELEVANT INFORMATION OF THE RESPONDENTS

This section provides the relevant information of the school heads and teachers at Cebu City Division in terms of their age, gender, civil status, highest educational attainment, length of service, performance rating, and relevant trainings, seminars, and workshops attended.

Age. Table 3 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of age.

Table 3
Age Profile

Age	Frequency (n=105)	Percentage
51 years old and above	13	12.3
41-50 years old	21	20
31-40 years old	45	42.8
23-30 years old	26	24.7
Total	105	100

In terms of the age profile of the respondent-groups, most of them belong to the age group of 31-40 years old, particularly 45 or 43% of them. 23-30-year-old respondents comprises of 26 or 25% of them. This is followed by 21 or 20% of them who fit in the age bracket of 41-50 years old, while 13 or 12% of the school heads and teachers are aged 51 years old and above.

Previous study indicates that teaching efficiency varies with the instructor's age and personality features. Murray (2016) investigated the extent to which personality qualities related with teaching efficacy change concomitantly with age, hence mediating the relationship between age and teaching. Peer assessments of 29 personality characteristics and archived student evaluations of teaching were acquired for 33 full-time psychology professors ranging in age from 33 to 64 using a cross-sectional methodology.

Teaching efficiency was shown to be inversely related to age and to substantially correspond with numerous personality factors. Consistent with the mediation hypothesis, personality qualities that linked favorably with teaching and decreased considerably with age (e.g., approval-seeking) were discovered; or personality traits that connected adversely with teaching and rose with age were detected (e.g., independent).

Gender. Table 4 reveals the profile of the respondents in terms of gender.

Table 4
Gender Profile

Gender	Frequency (n=105)	Percentage
Male	28	26.6
Female	77	73.3
Total	105	100

Meanwhile, in terms of their gender profile, there are 77 or 73% of the respondents who are female, while 28 or 27% of them are male school head- and teacher-respondents.

Women have traditionally been involved with school teaching. There has always been an ideological relationship between women's household roles and their careers as teachers. Traditionally, caring for younger children at school is viewed as an extension of parenting and hence regarded a natural employment for women (Ullah, 2019).

Females predominate in elementary schooling in the Philippines. According to the Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS), women made up 81% of the elementary and middle school teacher population in 2013, while men made up just 19% of the primary and middle school teacher population. Meanwhile, according to the World Bank's collection of development indicators derived from officially recognized sources, the proportion of primary school teachers in the Philippines was estimated to be 87.54 percent in 2017.

According to Abanica's (2015) research, some physical characteristics and features explain why women are regarded as less suited and attractive for specific tasks or projects. His study's findings also show that female respondents have fewer conventional ideas on gender roles than male respondents. Similarly, the concept that men and women have distinct biological and psychological features are clear, which leads to sex-role stereotyping, which limits their job mobility.

Civil Status. Table 5 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of civil status.

Table 5
Civil Status Profile

Civil Status	Frequency (n=105)	Percentage
Single	43	40.9
Married	59	56.1
Widow/Widower	3	2.85
Total	105	100

In relations to their civil status, 59 or 56% of the respondents are already married. Single respondents consist of 43 or 41% of the total respondents, while three (3) or 3% of them are either widow/widower.

Marriage is the start of a family and a lifelong commitment. It also allows them to develop selflessness as they serve their wife and children. Marriage is a spiritual and emotional bond as well as a physical union (Hunt, 2016).

This is corroborated by Mocheche's (2018) study, which found that marital status has an effect on job satisfaction, with married people being considerably happy in their occupations than unmarried people. According to the study, teacher counselors should use suitable cognitive behavioral therapy strategies to help divorced and single teachers improve their self-esteem and job happiness. Further research on gender and efficacy school management among secondary school administrators is suggested by this study.

Highest Educational Attainment. Table 6 indicates the highest educational attainment of the respondents.

Table 6
Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency (n=105)	Percentage
Doctorate Degree	6	5.71
With units in Doctorate Degree	7	6.66
Master's Degree	15	14.2
With units in Master's Degree	49	46.6
BSEEd/BSEEd graduate	26	24.7
Total	105	100

Looking into their highest educational attainment, most of the respondents obtained units in their master's degree, specifically 49 or 47% of them. 26 or 25% of the respondents are BSEEd/BSEEd graduates. Master's degree holder comprises of 15 or 14% of them, while respondents who obtained units in their doctorate degree; and are doctorate degree holder consist of seven (7) or 7%; and six (6) or 6% of them, respectively.

Pursuing a degree will most certainly be the one decision that is linked to both the most difficult and the most gratifying times in their lives. One of the most significant advantages of continuing education is that it may assist strengthen one's talents and help obtain new skills in preparation for professional growth and development (Sison, 2016).

The professors in this research undoubtedly prepared their students for the needed constant learning journey of someone who selected this vocation. Teachers are expected to never stop learning and to participate in learning activities that will help them better their skill. This is also a prerequisite for ranking among Department of Education personnel, which explains the statistics.

Length of Service. Table 7 presents the number of years in service of the respondents.

Table 7
Length of Service

Length of Service	Frequency (n=105)	Percentage
More than 6 years	54	51.4
4-6 years	15	14.2
1-3 years	28	26.6
Less than a year	8	7.61
Total	105	100

Delving into respondents' length of service, 54 or 51% of the total respondents have been linked with the institution for more than 6 years. This is followed by 28 or 27% of them who have been teaching for 1-3 years. Moreover, 15 or 14% of them have been working as school heads and teachers for 4-6 years, while eight (8) or 8% of the respondents have been associated with the school for less than a year.

Teacher experience in educational affairs is likely the most important factor in staff policies that affect current employees: it is a pillar of the traditional single-salary program; it supports policies for teacher transfer that prioritizes seniority; and it is widely regarded as a major source of inequity among schools. The fundamental assumption is that this experience enhances efficiency. Most people believe that teaching is a job that lasts a lifetime (Rey, 2017).

The respondents' years of service indicate that their knowledge, abilities, and productivity have grown with time. Teacher experience in educational affairs is likely the most important factor in staff policies that affect current employees: it is a pillar of the traditional single-salary program; it supports policies for teacher transfer that prioritize seniority; and it is widely regarded as a major source of inequity among schools. The employee's length of stay is a measurement or indicator of their contentment, and many workers choose to remain long when they are provided the necessary support and help, as well as the necessary perks and incentives (Jabdid, 2017).

Performance Rating. Table 8 reveals the performance rating of the respondents.

Table 8
Performance Rating

Performance Rating	Frequency (n=105)	Percentage
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Outstanding	-	-
Very Satisfactory	95	90.4
Satisfactory	10	9.52
Unsatisfactory	-	-
Poor	-	-
Total	105	100

When dealing with their performance rating, almost all of them gained a very satisfactory of performance rating, specifically 95 or 90% of them, while there are 10 or 10% of the respondent-groups who belong to the satisfactory level of performance rating.

High-quality teaching is critical for increasing student outcomes and closing achievement disparities. The Teacher Performance Appraisal System delivers meaningful appraisals to teachers, encouraging professional development and progress. The method is intended to promote teacher growth while also identifying possibilities for further help when necessary. The performance assessment process, through assisting teachers in reaching their full potential, is one component of Ontario's aim of achieving high levels of student success.

This is reinforced by Roberto's analysis (2019) of 'Teacher Quality in the Light of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers'. In addition, the results of the study revealed neither the skill nor the success of the teachers in terms of their sex and education, marital status, and job status. However, the overall results show that the level of teaching quality and the success of the students has a major connection.

Relevant Trainings, Seminars, and Workshops Attended. Table 9 shows the relevant trainings, seminars, and workshops attended by the respondents.

Table 9

Relevant Trainings, Seminars, and Workshops Attended

Relevant Trainings, Seminars, and Workshops Attended	Frequency (n=105)	Percentage	Rank
National	50	47.6	1 st
Division	26	24.7	2 nd
School	15	14.2	3 rd
Regional	7	6.66	4 th
District	5	4.76	5 th
International	2	1.90	6 th
Total	105	100	

When it comes to the relevant trainings, seminars, and workshops attended, 50 or 48% of them have been into national trainings, seminars, and workshops. Division trainings came next as it was attended by 25 or 26% of the respondents. Moreover, 15 or 14% of them have joined school trainings. Regional and district trainings followed with seven (7) or 7%; and five (5) or 5% of them, correspondingly. Meanwhile, international trainings, seminars, and workshops fell last as it only consist of two (2) or 2% of the total respondents.

The Department of Education's objective is for every teacher to become not just efficient but also effective. Today, a lot of training and seminars are being held in this objective to strengthen and grow the craft of each mentor in school. The Department fully recognizes that everything relies on instructors' capacity to put the learner at the center of every pupil's education (Felipe, 2018).

Education Secretary Leonor M. Briones has emphasized the need of suitable teacher training. According to her, relevant teacher trainings will provide educators with the necessary knowledge and expertise to sharpen the minds of Filipino students, as well as identify common and unique education problems and needs in Southeast Asian countries, and develop innovative and technology-based solutions to address these problems.

Trainings provide the following benefits: increased job satisfaction and morale among employees; increased employee motivation; increased efficiencies in processes resulting in financial gain; increased capacity to adopt new technologies and methods; increased innovation in strategies and products; reduced employee turnover; improved organizational image and risk management (Mcnamara, 2019).

EXTENT OF IMPLEMENTATION OF THE INDIVIDUAL PLAN OF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

The following tables reveal the extent of implementation of the individual plan of professional development towards career demand growth in terms of professional development in school; learning through professional

development; participation experience in IPPD; impact on learners; and attitude and beliefs in teaching and learning.

Professional Development in School. This provides a structured professional learning which results in changes in teacher classroom practices and improvements in learning outcomes at school.

Table 10
Professional Development in School

Items	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Legend
Meets my needs	4.31	Strongly Agree	4.21 - 5.00
Is offered at a time convenient for me	4.23	Strongly Agree	
Is offered by instructors who are knowledgeable and effective	4.41	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Is generally a positive experience	4.23	Strongly Agree	
Has positive impact on the organization as a whole	4.43	Strongly Agree	3.41 - 4.20
Has positive impact on the culture and climate in school	4.21	Strongly Agree	
Is often conducted during school day	4.14	Agree	Agree
Leads to in-service credit or stipend	4.17	Agree	
GRAND MEAN	4.26	Strongly Agree	2.61 -

3.40 Undecided
1.81 – 2.60 Disagree
1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree

In terms of professional development in school, it obtained a grand mean of 4.26, which means that the respondents strongly agree that the individual plan of professional development (IPPD) is effectively implemented and is perceived to increase their career demand growth.

Having positive impact on the organization as a whole got the highest weighted mean among all items with a weighted mean of 4.43. This is closely followed by professional development being offered by instructors who are knowledgeable and effective with a mean score of 4.41. Professional development being able to meet the needs of the respondents came next with a score of 4.31. Moreover, professional development being offered at a time convenient for teachers; and is generally a positive experience, got a weighted mean of 4.23, each. This is closely followed by professional development having a positive impact on the culture and climate in school with a score of 4.21. Meanwhile, professional development in school leading to in-service credit or stipend; and is often conducted during school day, fell last with the lowest weighted mean of 4.17; and 4.14, respectively.

Teaching is one of the few careers in which the least experienced members face the greatest challenges and the most responsibilities, (Brock and Gradly, 2015). The more the expertise the more the quality education teachers can provide. As Murray (2015), emphasized that experiences increases the teachers' productivity at all levels. Teaching experience has consistently been found teacher effectiveness.

Successful professional learning and development is consistently associated with professional learning communities (Schleicher, 2022). This is because professional learning communities can make a real difference to teachers' practice and pupil outcomes. Where they are properly constructed and have a persistent focus on improving learning outcomes, they help teachers to develop and to integrate new learning into their existing practice (Harris & Jones, 2021; Vescio, Ross & Adams, 2018; Wiliam, 2018; Hord, 2017).

Offering teachers the opportunity to participate and collaborate in professional learning communities is essential to high-quality professional development (Borko, Jacobs & Koellner, 2020; Little, 2016). Distributed leadership provides the infrastructure that holds professional learning communities together and makes them effective. The collective and interdependent work of educators at multiple levels, who are driving forward the innovative work, creates and sustains successful professional learning communities (Harris & Jones, 2021).

Developing and maintaining collaborative professional learning communities ensures that professional development is located within sustainable learning cultures and environments (Saunders, Goldenberg & Gallimore, 2019; Stoll et al, 2016). Professional learning communities can exist within and between schools. Such communities have a clear and shared understanding of effective teaching and learning that enhances learning for all pupils in their school or schools. The norm across the community is for colleagues to support each other in interrogating their practice critically, and there is a sense of collective responsibility for all colleagues' professional learning. Professional learning communities also foster change in practice by creating an environment that supports innovation and experimentation (Bryk, Camburn & Louis, 2015).

Learning through Professional Development. This helps educators to immediately identify learning problems, develop solutions, and promptly apply those solutions to address students' needs.

Table 11
Learning through Professional Development

<i>Because of professional development, I have learned:</i>	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Practical instructional strategies	4.2	Agree
New knowledge and skills	4.13	Agree
The new behind the practice	4.14	Agree
The new concepts connected to prior knowledge	4.14	Agree
GRAND MEAN	4.15	Agree

Meanwhile, in terms of learning through

professional development, it gained a grand mean of 4.15, which means that the respondents agree that the extent of implementation of the individual plan of professional development as it promotes professional development and continuous learning.

Learning practical instructional strategies came first with the highest weighted mean of 4.2. Learning the new behind the practice; and learning new concepts connected to prior knowledge, came next with a mean score of 4.14, while learning new knowledge and skills fell last with the lowest weighted mean among all items with 4.13.

This indicates that teachers learning through professional development are fully implemented. Hence, teaching is a dynamic profession, requires not only the development of a professional identity but the construction of professional knowledge and practice through continued professional learning (McCormack, Gore and Thomas, 2016). As professional, teachers are expected to maintain currency in a content knowledge and pedagogical-knowledge while as practicing teachers, the opportunity to maintain this, and to have this documented is by participating in school-system-or-state-organized professional development activities.

Individual and collective professional learning needs both have an explicit focus in studies of effective professional development (Ofsted, 2016). Individual needs relate both to the content of professional development, and also to teachers' personal concerns. Personal drivers such as life history, personal circumstances and professional life phase can affect teachers' needs at any particular time (Day et al, 2017; Grundy & Robinson, 2014), as well as learning needs, performance management and professional standards. When professional development is effective, it allows for a range of starting points and differentiates appropriately between diverse professional learning requirements (Loucks-Horsley & Matsumoto, 2015). It involves teachers in shaping their learning agenda and influencing the means by which this will be taken forward. Such development needs must also be matched to the best sources of support (Ofsted, 2016). Understanding specific needs helps promote ownership of professional learning which is essential for positive impact (Timperley et al, 2018).

To create consistently great pedagogy and widespread impact, team needs also have to be considered (Bubb, Earley & Hempel-Jorgensen, 2019). Professional development tends to be more effective when it is an integral part of a larger school improvement effort, rather than isolated activities that have little to do with other school initiatives or changes (Darling-Hammond et al, 2019). This is best set within a culture of professional learning where there is no tension between the respective needs of the individual, team and institution. Rather, there is a learning environment in which individual development contributes to the whole, and collaborative experiences and opportunities help to empower and provide meaningful and strategic context to the work of the individual.

Participation Experience in IPPD. This refers to direct observation of or participation of the teachers as a basis of their knowledge in IPPD.

Table 12

Participation Experience in IPPD

<i>After I have participated in a professional development experience, I usually:</i>	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Go back and experiment or practice with new instructional strategies	4.26	Strongly Agree
Implement/apply new instructional practices	4.32	Strongly Agree
Become committed to new teaching strategies	4.3	Strongly Agree
Note positive changes in my teaching	4.45	Strongly Agree
GRAND MEAN	4.33	Strongly Agree

Further more, in terms of participation experience

nce in IPPD, it collected a grand mean of 4.33, which means that the respondents strongly agree that the individual plan of professional development (IPPD) is effectively implemented and is perceived to increase their career demand growth.

Noting positive changes in their teaching came first among all items with the highest weighted mean of 4.45. This is followed by implementing or applying new instructional practices with a mean score of 4.32. Becoming committed to new teaching strategies gained a score of 4.3, while going back and experimenting or practicing with new instructional strategies fell last with the lowest weighted mean of 4.26.

Effective professional development enables teacher to work regularly together to improve their practice and implement strategies to meet the needs of the student. Teacher development has moved beyond simple in-service workshops and has experienced into a more robust system of continuing education. In a way, is new to teaching in that professional development and in-service training simply consisted of workshops or short term courses that offered teachers new information on specific aspects of their work (Brookfield, 2015). Champion (2013) posited that regular opportunities and experiences for professional development over the past few years had yielded systematic growth and development in the teaching profession.

Impact on Learners. This pertains to how IPPD of teachers results to the advancement of knowledge, capabilities, and attitude of their learners.

Table 13

Impact on Learners

<i>Generally, my professional development impacts my students in the following ways:</i>	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Makes positive impact on my students' learning	4.48	Strongly Agree
Student achievement increases	4.23	Strongly Agree
Classroom management has improved	4.37	Strongly Agree
Student achievement has risen on state or districts assessments	4.12	Agree
GRAND MEAN	4.32	Strongly Agree

Delving into impact on

learners, it garnered a grand mean of 4.32, which means that the respondents strongly agree that the IPPD implementation has a great impact on promoting self-directed learning among the students and effective classroom management facilitated by able teachers.

Making positive impact on students' learning got the highest weighted mean under this indicator with a weighted mean of 4.48. Having classroom management being improved, came next with a mean score of 4.37. This is followed by increasing the achievement of learners with a score of 4.23, while having learners' achievement rising on state or district assessments got the lowest weighted mean of 4.12.

Based on the result of data in this indicator, professional development involves its relationship to student achievement. In support to this, Marzano (2003) concluded that the professional development activities experienced by teachers have similar impact on student achievement.

Professional Development has been defined by some scholars such as Avalos (2021) as a continuous process of teachers' learning including the process of how they learn and apply their knowledge to support students. The process of teachers' learning can be planned and unplanned, formal and informal, thus participating in various courses, reflecting on their own teaching, observing other teachers' teaching, conversations with other colleagues before or after teaching (Postholm, 2022).

Some scholars (Barber and Mourshed, 2017) also assert that improving instruction is the only way to improve students' achievement and that there should always be a balance between the quality of an education system and teachers' quality. To achieve students' outcome, teachers' quality and development should not be compromised. Yoon et al. (2017) revealed that teacher PD has tremendous ramifications on students' learning achievement in three ways. Firstly, PD improved teachers' knowledge and skills; also, teachers acquire effective knowledge and skills, which eventually enhance their teaching, and lastly, PD helps teachers with teaching skills which lead to better students' learning outcomes.

Research has also shown that there can be tremendous improvement in teachers' instructional methods if teachers actively participate in PD activities (Archibald, Cogshall, Croft, & Goe, 2021; Yoon et al., 2017). Notwithstanding, Darling-Harmaond et al. (2019) believed that such PD programs should be intensive,

continuous and connected to practice so that they would achieve the effective changes significant for the on-going improvement of teachers' practice and students' outcome (Lindstrom & Speck, 2014).

Attitudes and Beliefs. This refers to the core values and beliefs the teacher-respondents hold internally when teaching through IPPD.

Table 14
Attitudes and Beliefs

Items	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
I learned practical instructional strategies	4.32	Strongly Agree
My teaching becomes more effective	4.51	Strongly Agree
I am more efficient or productive as a teacher	4.14	Agree
I have enjoyed the experience	4.47	Strongly Agree
I become empowered in new ways	4.14	Agree
I have learned to meet the various needs of all of my students	4.17	Agree
It has a positive impact on student behavior	4.28	Strongly Agree
My students become more actively engaged in learning	4.34	Strongly Agree
I can see a positive impact on student achievement	4.35	Strongly Agree
It impacts my annual performance evaluations positively	4.44	Strongly Agree
GRAND MEAN	4.31	Strongly Agree

Lastly, in terms of attitude and beliefs, it collected to a grand mean of 4.31, which means that the respondents strongly agree that the extent of implementation of the individual plan of professional development promote positive impact on the competence of the teachers as well as observable improvement in how engaged the students have become in class.

Having teaching becomes more effective in the implementation of IPPD came first with the highest weighted mean of 4.51. This is followed by teachers enjoying the experience; and having IPPD impacting their annual performance evaluations positively, with mean scores of 4.47; and 4.44, correspondingly. Moreover, teachers who see positive impact on student achievement came next with a score of 4.35, while closely followed by students becoming more actively engaged in learning; and being able to learn practical instructional strategies with weighted mean of 4.34; and 4.32, respectively. IPPD positively impacting students' behavior gained a mean score of 4.28, while IPPD making teachers become more efficient and productive, fell last with the lowest score among all items with 4.14.

This supports that professional development goal is to provide opportunities for teachers to learn and grow within the profession, thereby making an impact to the students learning. PD has been articulated by some scholars (Griffin, 2013) as any designed activity meant to change the beliefs and practices of the teacher profession and understanding of school persons toward an articulated end" such as improved student performance. It follows that PD can be seen as effective if the end results are met and improved teacher practices and students outcomes (Desimone et al., 2012; Hill, 2019).

Scholars (Lindstrom & Speck, 2014; Elmore, 2012) are of the view that PD is an on-going collaborative sharing of professional knowledge among teachers on the current trends of issue concerning the teaching job in order to keep teachers formed and informed. Some researches classify PD into formal and informal. According to Yoon et al. (2017) formal PD programs include trainings, courses, or other instructional activities conducted to support teachers' continuing education and inspire positive change in their teaching. For Postholm (2022), teachers reflecting on their own teaching, observing other teachers' teaching, conversations with other colleagues before or after teaching are classified as informal PD.

Summary. This presents the summary of the extent of implementation of the individual plan of professional development towards career demand growth in terms of professional development in school; learning through professional development; participation experience in IPPD; impact on learners; and attitude and beliefs.

Table 15
Summary

Items	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Professional Development in School	4.26	Strongly Agree

Learning Through Professional Development	4.15	Agree
Participation Experience in IPPD	4.33	Strongly Agree
Impact on Learners	4.32	Strongly Agree
Attitude and Beliefs	4.31	Strongly Agree
OVERALL GRAND MEAN	4.27	Strongly Agree

Legend

4.21 – 5.00

Strongly

- Agree
- 3.41 – 4.20 Agree
- 2.61 – 3.40 Undecided
- 1.81 – 2.60 Disagree
- 1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree

The extent of implementation of the individual plan of professional development (IPPD) is divided into five indicators – professional development in school; learning through professional development; participation experience in IPPD; impact on learners; and attitude and beliefs. This accumulated an overall grand mean of 4.27, which means that the respondents strongly agree that the extent of implementation of the IPPD increases their career demand growth.

Of the five indicators, participation experience in individual plan of professional development (IPPD) got the highest weighted mean of 4.33. This is closely followed by impact on learners; and attitude and beliefs in IPPD with mean scores of 4.32; and 4.31, correspondingly. Moreover, professional development in school got a weighted mean of 4.26, while learning through professional development obtained the lowest score of 4.15.

The extent of implementation of teachers individual professional development in this study is characterized being linked to the districts goals and improvement; aligned with the teachers’ experiences and evaluation process; is offered during school day; has an impact within the districts climates and culture; students achievement; empowered strategies, skills and new techniques in teaching. The respondents who have experienced and been through professional development activities can attest to the positive impact of IPPD on their career.

TESTING OF RELATIONSHIP

Profile of the Respondents and Extent of Implementation of IPPD. The following tables uncover the results of testing the relationship between the profile of the teacher-respondents and the extent of implementation of individual plan for professional development towards career demand growth.

Table 16
Profile of Respondents and Extent of Implementation of IPPD

Profiles	Computed Value		Critical p-value	df	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Age Profile and Extent of Implementation of IPPD	<i>r</i>	.397*	.003		Rejected	Significant
Gender Profile and Extent of Implementation of IPPD	χ^2	21.41	.720	26	Accepted	Not Significant
Civil Status Profile and Extent of Implementation of IPPD	χ^2	13.79	.388	13	Accepted	Not Significant
Length of Service and Extent of Implementation of IPPD	<i>r</i>	.395*	.002		Rejected	Significant
Highest Educational Attainment and Extent of Implementation of IPPD	<i>r</i>	.227	.095		Rejected	Significant

@ 0.05 level of significance

Table 16 presents the testing of relationship between the profile of the respondents and the extent of implementation of individual plan for professional development. It is gleaned on the table that age, length of service, and highest educational attainment profiles of the teacher-respondents obtained critical value lower than 0.05 level of significance, with .003, 0.002 and .095, respectively. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that age, length of service and highest educational attainment of the teachers are significantly related with their extent of implementation of individual plan for professional development.

The results of the study simply mean that the gender and civil status profiles of teachers have not influenced the extent of implementation of individual plan and professional development of teachers while age, length of service, and highest educational attainment have an impact to the IPPD of the respondents. Hence, there is a significant relationship to the extent of implementation of individual plan and professional development. Therefore, these things are important in the proposed action plan for the implementation of individual plan for professional development. However, a factor such as financial aspects, time, and priorities in life affects the implementation of the IPPD.

Discussion

Findings of this study reveal that the school heads and teacher-respondents belong to the age group of 31-40 years old, female, married, obtained units in their master's degree, have been linked with the institution for more than 6 years, have a performance rating of very satisfactory, and attended national trainings, seminars, and workshops.

Looking into the extent of implementation of the individual plan of professional development (IPPD) which is divided into five indicators – professional development in school; learning through professional development; participation experience in IPPD; impact on learners; and attitude and beliefs accumulated an overall grand mean of 4.27, which means that the respondents strongly agree that the extent of implementation of the IPPD across all indicators increases their career demand growth.

When testing the relationship between the profile of respondents and extent of implementation of individual plan for professional development, age, length of service, and highest educational attainment rejected the null hypothesis which means that these profiles of teachers are significantly related with their extent of implementation of individual plan for professional development.

In terms of the focus group discussion, the teachers reveal that the implementation of IPPD gives greater insights and improves performance; allows putting into practice the appropriate trainings, and seminars attended; and impacts students' learning and behavior.

Lastly, pertaining to the challenges and barriers in the implementation of the individual plan of professional development, most of the teacher-respondents believe that time constraint is their main challenge or barrier in terms of the implementation of the IPPD towards career demand growth for the public secondary school teachers.

Conclusion

Based on the salient findings of the study, it can be concluded that the age, length of service, and highest educational attainment of the teacher-respondents resulted into the rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that it gained a positive correlation. This means that the older or more mature the teacher becomes, the longer they have stayed in the school they are connected with, and the higher their educational achievement, the more they positive perceive the positive impact of the individual plan for professional development (IPPD) has on their teaching competence and career.

Moreover, the respondents believe that time constraint is their main problem in the implementation of the IPPD and strongly believe that IPPD gives greater insights and improves their performance; allows putting into practice the appropriate trainings, and seminars attended; and impacts students' learning and behavior.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions derived from the findings of the study, the following are recommended:

1. The proposed output of this study will be utilized in the research environment where this study was conducted;
2. School administrators may consider conducting seminar and workshop on the relevant topics and activities related to IPPD implementation and instructional effectiveness;
3. A comprehensive IPPD implementation guide be in placed so that teachers will be easily guided on how to make the most out of this initiative;
4. Further researchers may consider other locale and respondents to validate the current investigation; and
5. The Department of Education train school heads to see research results as guide in refining IPPD implementation and effectiveness.

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